

2 Poems by Ketaki Dutta

Broken Dreams

She dreamt of being an apothecary,
With lady medics few and far between—
She wished to throw off her veil
While treating the ailing women.
The moon bobbed up to hide
 Behind the fronds of palm,
Her wish came to be true
The wish she made on the milky moon!

Grabbing the certificate, she went
 To serve the humanity.
Oh Alas! But it stood in jeopardy!
Laila knew not what to do
With her *hijab*,
With her trampled aspirations!

She took the veil up
Covered her face with it,
Persona non-grata as she was,
With her identity veiled,
Negated rather by the loud diktats
 Of the impending Terror!
Peace was she dreamt of now,
Peace was what she prayed for
Other women would come in tow
To cry themselves hoarse ...Or?

APOCALYPSE

All lights of the world
 Had been soaked by the
 Black sun,
This sun was about to lose
 Its sheen, its golden rays,
 Its heat, its warmth!
The earth kept entering
 Into a miasma of jarring sounds,
 All objects crumbled into
 smithereens of nullity,
 it seemed.
The vault of heaven crushed
 Into small pieces,
 Showering on dorps and cities—
The noisy concussion
Brought in a horrible
APOCALYPSE!!

Bio:

Ketaki Datta [Ph.D] is an Associate Professor in English of a Govt. College, Kolkata, India, to be precise. She is a novelist, translator, book reviewer [with Compulsive Reader, USA, and Muse India, Hyderabad, India], and a poet. She has two novels, “A Bird Alone” and “One Year for Mourning”, the last being published by Partridge Publishing Co. USA. Book of short stories is in press. Her stories have been widely anthologized. Her book of poems, “Across the Blue Horizon” was published by Feedaread Publishing, U.K. aided by Arts Council, England. Her book of poems with Prof. Wilfried Raussert has been published from Germany titled, “Urban Reflections: A Dialogue in Poetry and Photography”. Her latest book of poems “The Music of Eternity” has been published in India by Penprints Publications. Her translated novels are three in number, “The Last Salute” being published from Sahitya Akademi, New Delhi, India. She has academic books to her credit too. She went to Lisbon[Cidade Universitaria], Univ. of Oxford and Univ. of California [Santa Barbara] to present her research papers on invitation. “Oral Stories of the Totos”, a research work on the tribals has been published by Sahitya Akademi. Her recent short story collection is “ Unshared Secret and Other Stories”.